

Weedy Rice Response to Clethodim

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Introduction

- Weedy rice (*Oryza* spp.) is an important weed of cultivated rice because it is a close relative.
- There are 5 weedy rice accessions in California which are likely the result of wild, weedy, and cultivated rice parentage from within and outside of California [1].
- There are no labeled herbicides for control of weedy rice in California.
- Barnyardgrass (*Echinochloa crus-galli*), late watergrass (*Echinochloa oryzicola*), early watergrass (*Echinochloa oryzoides*), and sprangletop (*Leptochloa fascicularis*) are important weedy grasses and are difficult to control with current available herbicides due to increase in herbicide-resistant populations.
- Clethodim is an ACCase inhibiting cyclohexanedione herbicide that effectively control grasses [2].

Objective

- To determine the response of California weedy rice accessions and weedy grasses to clethodim herbicide applications.

Figure 1. Clethodim dose response on weedy rice accessions.

Materials and Methods

- Weedy rice accession 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, and two rice variety as M105 and M206 were utilized.
- Junglerice, barnyardgrass, late watergrass, early watergrass, and sprangletop were grass weed materials.
- Clethodim application rates were 0, 9.4, 18.8, 37.5, 75, 150, 300, and 600 g ai ha⁻¹.
- The experiment was conducted on a randomized block design with 5 replications in the UC Davis greenhouse facilities.
- The herbicide was applied with 0.25% nonionic surfactant (% v/v).
- Dose-response curves based on the log-logistic model were used to determine the effective dose that provides 90% control (ED₉₀).
- The sprayer chamber was calibrated to deliver 187 L ha⁻¹ application volume at 275 kPa pressure. Observations were taken 28 DAT.

Figure 2: The effect of the clethodim herbicide on rice at 28 days after treatment. Control, 1/8x, 1/4x, 1/2x, 1x, 2x, and 4x are equal to 0, 9, 18, 38, 75, 150, 300, and 600 g ai ha⁻¹, respectively. Accession 4 was the most susceptible but accession 5 was the most tolerant in the weedy rice.

Result and Discussion

- The clethodim rates that cause 90% plant injury (ED₉₀) were 58, 61, 59, 50, and 74 g ai ha⁻¹ for weedy rice accessions 1, 2, 3, 4, and 5, respectively.
- Accession 5 was the most tolerant, but accession 3 was the most susceptible to clethodim in the California weedy rice population.
- M206 and M105 variety ED₉₀ was 106 and 87 g ai ha⁻¹ for cultivated rice.
- Clethodim ED₉₀ values were 54, 43, 46, 75, and 80 g ai ha⁻¹ for junglerice, barnyardgrass, late watergrass, early watergrass, and sprangletop, respectively.
- Sprangletop was the most tolerant, and barnyardgrass was the most susceptible to clethodim in rice-weeds.

Figure 3. The effect of the clethodim herbicide on weeds at 28 days after treatment. From left to right in each photo, control, 1/16x, 1/8x, 1/4x, 1/2x, 1x, 2x, and 4x are equal to 0, 9, 18, 38, 75, 150, 300, and 600 g ai ha⁻¹, respectively. Barnyardgrass (top right) was the most susceptible but accession sprangletop (bottom left) was the most tolerant in the weeds.

Table 1. Clethodim dose-response results and curves based on the log-logistic model to ED₅₀-ED₉₀

Plants	GR50	GR90
Weedy Rice 1	34	58
Weedy Rice 2	54	61
Weedy Rice 3	52	59
Weedy Rice 4	15	50
Weedy Rice 5	19	74
Junglerice (<i>Echinochloa colona</i>)	43	54
Barnyardgrass (<i>Echinochloa crus-galli</i>)	36	43
Late watergrass (<i>Echinochloa oryzicola</i>)	38	46
Early watergrass (<i>Echinochloa oryzoides</i>)	47	75
Sprangletop (<i>Leptochloa fascicularis</i>)	48	80
Rice (M105)	49	87
Rice (M206)	37	106

Conclusion

- Clethodim effectively controlled weedy rice and weedy grasses.
- Clethodim is able to control between 43-80 gr ai ha⁻¹ and an average of 60 gr ai ha⁻¹ dose by 90% for both weedy rice and weedy grasses.
- Sprangletop was determined as the most tolerant among the tested plants.
- These findings indicate clethodim has great potential to be used as a spot treatment for the management of weedy rice and grass.

References

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